
**THE EFFECT OF PEDAGOGIC COMPETENCY AND COMPETENCE ON
PROFESSIONAL TEACHER PERFORMANCE IN PADANG PARIAMAN
REGENCY PRIVATE VOCATIONAL SCHOOL**

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Abstract:

Research Objective to analyze how much influence pedagogic competence, professional competence on the performance of Public Middle Schools in Padang Pariaman Regency. Quantitative research uses data analysis using a regression correlation. The results of the study: (1) The effect of pedagogic competence on performance is 46,8%, (2) The influence of professional competence on performance is 50,3%. (3) There is a positive effect jointly between pedagogical competence and professional competence in teacher performance by 53%. Conclusion of the study: Pedagogic competence, professional competence influence teacher performance in Padang Pariaman Regency.

Keywords: Education; Pedagogic Competency; Profesional Competency; Teacher Performamce.

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1. Introduction

Educational institutions have a great responsibility to deliver students to the destination far enough and not easy to achieve. A teacher must be able to bring students to a critical way of thinking, so that they can creatively solve their own problems and find a way out, so as to realize an active and independent way of learning. In the everyday reality, it cannot be denied that there are still many subject teachers who teach in an unprofessional way. Or it could also not understand in depth the benefits, uses and principles of the subjects being taught, because the teacher in the school is required to teach and educate until the achievement of educational goals. In the teaching and learning process, teachers lack opportunities and freedom for students to do and think creatively, students are left passive to receive what is given, not given freedom and less monitored. From the results of education like this, it can be seen that there are many people who are less able to adjust to the demands of society and development, always be rigid, not creative and even lack discipline.

At this time the government has provided many allowances for teachers in each region, but still the achievements and motivation of children are still lacking to study seriously. We both know that in large cities, there are so many thugs with mentality and no morality that are characterized

by their behavior that likes fighting and skipping school hours. Writers from the Padang Pariaman area, West Sumatra had previously felt and judged that students in the writer's area were far from frivolous and even low moral, because the authors knew that the daily life in the Minang realm was not an everyday thing that they could. But in reality at the present time, students there now are following the trend of brawl and recklessness. This raises many questions, what is wrong with education and morals from the successors of this nation. Some answers to the possibility of changing attitudes from students are the possibility that the teacher is less able to transfer moral understanding and learning correctly and well. Which results in students often skipping even being able to pick up things like the brawl.

For this reason, the number of government policies for education in Indonesia, including character education, requires teachers to be able to overcome problems that occur and are experienced by students themselves. But why does this seem to make the atomic bomb turn around for education in Indonesia, of course. Therefore in the Law it is explained that the teacher must have four competencies that are very important to be mastered by the teacher. Because the teacher is an educator who is also responsible for delivering students to be able to compete in the era of globalization and avoid an attitude that is not commendable. To be able to carry out the competency obligations properly, the government held a Teacher Competency Test (UKG) program. It was also proven from the Singgalang Daily newspaper, the head of the West Sumatra Education Agency, H. Burhasman, revealed that from the data of equivalent high school teachers now managed by the province it was found that the UKG value was 63.5. the realm of competence that must be fulfilled by teachers, namely pedagogic, professional, personality, and social competencies, is related to each other. Often skipping during school days becomes a possibility that it happens as a result of the boredom of students following a subject in that school. This will lead to the opinion that the subject teacher is not able to carry out one of these competencies properly. So that these students feel they have not benefited and are lazy to take the truant path during the lesson. In Minangkabau culture, the procedures in daily life have their rules with a sufficiently thick portion and must be followed. Even for education, science gets special attention from Minangkabau natural culture. In the Minangkabau community, certainly having a high education is the main thing that must be achieved in such away. "Alam Takambang Jadi Guru" is a proverb that comes from Minangkabau. If it is used as an Indonesian language, it roughly becomes "the developed world used as a teacher". Today, the saying is included in the learning motto for teachers. In the Minang domain, the expression is very communicative. Indeed this saying or philosophical expression implies, first showing one's attitude towards the responsibilities that he should have carried out in the context of self-development. Both of these expressions mean to show us what the source of knowledge and skills is. Alam Takambang that is addressing the real source of learning, namely learning resources that can truly fulfill all needs that are always present throughout the ages.

Many of the advanced technologies that we use today take the principle of work from this nature. Alam Takambang Becomes the Teacher the most appropriate understanding for this is "nature" (also with Indonesian) which is "Takambang" (widespread) or this universe with all its contents. So the teacher is interpreted as "teacher" (same as Indonesian). The teacher means what can give us a lesson or what we can learn from it. Teacher competence is comprehensive and is a unity that is mutually interconnected and mutually supportive, but in the learning process, pedagogical competence has a very important role because it is directly related to the main task of a teacher,

namely as the manager of the learning process. Pedagogic competence is an ability that is possessed by the teacher so that his task as an educator can be carried out well because in managing learning carried out by teachers who do not have this competence, it will be difficult to achieve the desired learning goals. However, several problems have been noted in the competence of teachers at present. According to the results of the Teacher Competency Test (UKG) quoted from Tempo electronic news, there are still many teachers who are below the expected standard. The Head of the Human Resources Development and Quality Assurance Agency of the Ministry of Education and Culture, Syawal Gultom, said that the national average value calculated from July 1, 2012, was 47.84. Shawwal said the ideal value is 65. This is the standard set for students if they want to get a complete predicate in a subject. "The teacher should be above (the standard)," he said. And also the level of education in Indonesia which is still low is evidenced from data reported by Detik News online news that UNESCO data in the 2016 Global Education Monitoring (GEM) Report shows that education in Indonesia is only ranked 10th out of 14 developing countries. While an important component in education is the teacher ranks 14th out of 14 developing countries in the world. The teacher must be able to carry out his role professionally in answering the challenges of the problems faced in his duties. Quoted from online media between West Sumatra based on the data we have, reports of people who complain about the problem of the education sector in West Sumatra from 2013 to 2014 doubled, "said Head of West Sumatra Ombudsman, Yunafri in Padang, Monday. 2013 received 23 reports, while 2014 increased to 47. The role of teachers in the overall education program in schools to achieve educational goals is optimally dominant, namely, to educate, foster and develop the potential of students, teachers need to determine teaching, suitable material and under the ability of students to achieve the objectives that have been formulated. . In the 2015 UKG results, it was noted that the pedagogical and professional values of teachers in West Sumatra were number 42 out of 68 provinces in Indonesia. With things like that everyone will get the opportunity for lifelong learning because it is supported by the availability of learning resources everywhere. It also implies that a teacher who teaches taking lessons is also from Takambang Nature. Alam Takambang is used as a teacher not a matter of far or near because with the help of technology many things become very easy. There have been many government programs to advance teacher performance to become professional and reliable in the competencies that teachers must-have. The symptoms that I found indicate the teacher's low pedagogical competence and teacher's professional competence. This makes the writer interested in conducting scientific research to find out how much the influence of Pedagogic Competence and Professional Competence on Teacher Performance in Padang Pariaman District Middle School.

2. Materials and Methods

This study uses quantitative approaches, survey methods, and causal techniques. The affordable population in this study were teachers of Public Middle Schools in Padang Pariaman Regency, totaling 976 junior high school teachers from 58 Padang Pariaman District Public Middle Schools based on data from the Padang Pariaman District Education Office. But after being processed using the Slovin formula, the samples obtained were 100 respondents. The data collection technique in this study is by using a questionnaire that contains a list of statements. This list of statements was then distributed to be filled out by the respondents. The filling out of this questionnaire is closed, and in the list of statements several alternative answers have been provided so that the respondent can choose the answer that best fits the real conditions he

experiences. The technique of data collection is done by collecting respondents to fill in the questions contained in the research instrument. The instruments in this study must be tested first to determine the validity and reliability of the instrument. The trial of this instrument is intended to refine the instrument to obtain the validity and reliability of the items in the research instrument.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Analysis of Testing

1) Pedagogic Competence on Teacher Performance

a) Normality Test of Variable X₁ to Variable Y

Table 1.1: Normality Test Kolmogorov-Smirnov Variable X₁ to Variable Y

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
		Unstandardized Residual	
N		100	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0,0000000	
	Std. Deviation	8,31338735	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,073	
	Positive	0,073	
	Negative	-0,067	
Test Statistic		0,073	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200c, d	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed)	Sig.	,641e	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0,629
		Upper Bound	0,653

Based on the results of the above output, a statistical test of 0,073 was obtained, and in the Asymp line. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.200 or can be written as a probability value (p-value) = 0.200 > 0.05 or H₀ accepted. So that the data is said to be normally distributed at $\alpha = 0.05$.

2) Professional Competence on Teacher Performance

b) Normality Test of Variable X₂ to Variable Y

Table 1.1: Normality Test Kolmogorov-Smirnov Variable X₂ to Variable Y

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0,0000000
	Std. Deviation	8,03509678
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,057
	Positive	0,057
	Negative	-0,053
Test Statistic		0,057

Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)			,200c, d
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed)	Sig.		,886e
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0,878
		Upper Bound	0,894

Based on the above output, a statistical test of 0.057 and the Asymp line was obtained. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.200 or can be written as a probability value (p-value) = 0.200 > 0.05 or H0 accepted. So that the data is said to be normally distributed at $\alpha = 0.05$.

3.1.2. Hypothesis Testing

1) Pedagogic Competence on Performance

a) Regression Model

Based on the results of the calculation of the regression model X_1 against Y, it is known that the constant value is 42,346 while the value of B (beta) is 0.589 so that the regression equation formed: $Y = 42,346 + 0,589X_1$.

Table 1.5: ANOVA regression model $Y = 42,346 + 0,589X_1$

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	42,346	10,687		3,962	0,000
	Pedagogic	0,589	0,063	0,684	9,280	0,000

b) Test of Significance

The calculation results show that $F_{count} = 86.125$ with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. Can be seen in the following table:

Table 1.6: ANAVA for the significance of the model $Y = 42,346 + 0,589X_1$

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	6013,031	1	6013,031	86,125	,000b
	Residual	6842,129	98	69,818		
	Total	12855,160	99			

c) Linearity Test

From the results of the linearity test it is known that $F_{hit} = 0.969 < 1.46$. These results can be seen in the linearity table between pedagogic and performance competencies below:

Table 1.7: Variable X_1 Linearity Test Results against Y

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	0,05	0,01
performance * Pedagogic	Between Groups	(Combined)	8753,027	41	213,488	3,019		
		Linearity	6013,031	1	6013,031	85,018		
		Deviation from Linearity	2739,995	40	68,500	0,969	1,46	1,70
	Within Groups	4102,133	58	70,726				
	Total	12855,160	99					

Visually the regression model can be seen through the following picture:

Figure 1.1: Regression Line Diagram $Y = 42,346 + 0,589X_1$

d) Correlation Coefficient

From the results of the correlation coefficient test between the variables X_1 and the Y variable, the results show that the path coefficient in this test is 0.684 which can be seen in the following table:

Table 1.8: Variable Coefficient Coefficient X_1 with Y

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part
1 (Constant)	42,346	10,687		3,962	0,000	21,139	63,554			
X_1	0,589	0,063	0,684	9,280	0,000	0,463	0,715	0,684	0,684	0,684

e) Coefficient of Determination

Based on the results of the correlation coefficient of 0.684, it can be concluded that the value of the determination coefficient is 46.80%.

2) Professional Competence on Performance

a) Regression Model

Based on the results of the calculation of the regression model X_2 against Y it is known that the constant value is 58,042 while the value of b is 0.598 so that the regression equation formed: $Y = 58,042 + 0,598X_2$.

Table 1.9: ANOVA regression model $Y = 58,042 + 0,598X_2$

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	58,042	8,422		6,892	0,000
Professional	0,598	0,060		9,922	0,000

b) Significance Test

The calculation results show that Fcount = 98.454, can be seen in the following table:

Table 1.10: ANAVA for the significance of the model $Y = 58,042 + 0,598X_2$

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6442,423	1	6442,423	98,454	,000b
	Residual	6412,737	98	65,436		
	Total	12855,160	99			

c) Linearity Test

From the results of the linearity test it is known that $F_{hit} = 0.959 < 1.46$. These results can be seen in the linearity table between pedagogic and performance competencies below:

Table 1.11: Variable X2 Linearity Test Results against Y

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	0,05	0,01
performance * Professional	Between Groups	(Combined)	9137,436	43	212,499	3,201	
		Linearity	6463,361	1	6463,361	97,357	
		Deviation from Linearity	2674,075	42	63,668	0,959	1,46
	Within Groups		3717,724	56	66,388		
Total			12855,160	99			

Visually the regression model can be seen through the following picture:

Figure 1.2: Regression Line Diagram $Y = 58,042 + 0,598X_2$

d) Correlation Coefficient

From the results of the test of the correlation coefficient between the variables X1 and the Y variable, the results show that the path coefficient in this test is 0.709. The results of the correlation coefficient test can be seen in the table below:

Table 1.12: Variable X2 Correlation Test for Y

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	
1	(Constant)	55,599	8,639		6,436	0,000	38,455	72,742			
	X2	0,614	0,062	0,709	9,955	0,000	0,492	0,737	0,709	0,709	0,709

e) Coefficient of Determination

Based on the results of the correlation coefficient of 0.709, the value of the determination coefficient is 50.2%.

3) Pedagogic Competence and Professional Competence on Performance

a) Regression Model

Based on the calculation results of the regression models X1 and X2 towards Y, it is known that the constant value a (X1) is 0.260 and a (X2) 0.383 while the b value is 44.209 so the regression equation can be written as follows: $Y = 44.209 + 0.260X1 + 0.383X2$.

Table 1.13: ANOVA regression model $Y = 44.209 + 0.260X1 + 0.383X2$

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	44,209	10,130		4,364	0,000
	Pedagogik	0,260	0,111	0,302	2,345	0,021
	Profesional	0,383	0,109	0,454	3,516	0,001

b) Test of Significance

The calculation results show that F Calculate = 54,235 can be seen in the following table:

Table 1.14: ANAVA for the significance of the model $Y = 44.209 + 0.260X1 + 0.383X2$.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	6786,359	2	3393,179	54,235	,000b
	Residual	6068,801	97	62,565		
	Total	12855,160	99			

c) Linearity Test

From the results of the linearity test it is known that the linearity value of the deviation is $1.132 > 0.05$. These results can be seen in the linearity table between pedagogic competencies and professional competencies towards performance below:

Table 1.15: Linearity Test of Variables X1 and Variable X₂ towards Y

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
X2 * X1	Between Groups	(Combined)	14247,560	41	347,501	7,004	0,000
		Linearity	12000,107	1	12000,107	241,858	0,000
		Deviation from Linearity	2247,453	40	56,186	1,132	0,328

	Within Groups	2877,750	58	49,616	
	Total	17125,310	99		

d) Correlation Coefficient

Based on the model table the correlation coefficient variables X_1 and X_2 towards Y get a value of 0.530.

Table 1.16: Correlation Coefficients of variables X_1 and X_2 towards Y

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,728a	0,530	0,520	7,892	0,530	54,704	2	97	0,000

e) Coefficient of Determination

Based on the results of the correlation coefficient of 0.530, it can be concluded that the value of the determination coefficient is 28.1%.

4. Discussion

The results of testing the first hypothesis showed a positive result between pedagogical competence and teacher performance with a correlation coefficient of 0.684. That is, the higher the value of a teacher's pedagogic competence will affect the high performance of the teacher. Teacher's pedagogic competency shows the teacher's ability to related to learning techniques in the classroom. The more pedagogically competent, the higher the mastery of teaching classes. This can affect teacher performance in the classroom. The results of this study are by previous research from Mulyasa [1] which said that pedagogic competence is important because it determines the success of the learning process which is directly focused on learning abilities including student management, implementation, planning, evaluation of student learning outcomes and development of potential students. And also research from Hakim [2] also suggests that pedagogic competence has a positive influence on teacher performance.

Then on the results of testing the second hypothesis, it shows a positive result between professional competence and teacher performance with a correlation coefficient of 0.709. That is, the higher the value of a teacher's professional competence will affect the high results of the teacher's performance. The results of this study are also in line with Rahman's research [3], namely the quality of teachers can be seen from the mastery of teachers in the subject area and their ability to manage the substance of academic learning and develop its potential.

And the results of testing the third hypothesis show the existence of a positive result between pedagogic competence and professional competence on teacher performance with a correlation coefficient of 0.530. This means that teachers who have good pedagogical competencies will have good professional competencies and that will certainly greatly affect the teacher's performance. Due to pedagogical and professional competencies are competencies that both determine that a teacher is competent in his field. The results obtained are under previous studies by several researchers such as Supriyatno [4] who stated that teacher competence can improve Teacher Performance. Besides, the findings in the Bintarti study [5] suggest that the level of competence has a sufficiently positive relationship with the performance of the teaching staff.

Also, Hafid's research [6] which states that Teacher Competence has a positive influence on teacher performance. Mulyasa's research results in Salmawati [7] teacher performance assessment is a series of performance assessment programs designed to identify teacher competencies, especially relating to pedagogical competencies and professional competencies related to planning, implementation and assessment of learning through measurement of competency mastery shown in teacher performance or teacher performance, both directly and indirectly.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusions

Pedagogic competencies with teacher performance influence each other by 0.468 and there is a positive and significant influence between professional competence and teacher performance of 0.503. And there is a positive and significant influence between pedagogical and professional competence with teacher performance of 0.530.

5.2. Recommendations

It is expected that the principal, is expected to give more attention to subject teachers in carrying out learning in school. Both in terms of morale and trying together so that the facilities and infrastructure to support learning can be a useful medium for the interests of education in schools. Subject teachers are expected to be more serious in understanding and interpreting the meaning of the goals of national education and seriously to become competent teachers in their fields. And more willing to learn to be more creative and active to provide a stimulus for enthusiasm in learning students at school. For further research, it should research the implementation of teacher's pedagogical and professional competencies towards the learning process in Padang Pariaman Middle School using different and broader research methods, so that teacher competencies can be more widely known.

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